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Calabar Cultural Festival and Black Atlantic Carnival Aesthetics in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Every year since 2004, Calabar the city capital of Cross River State, Nigeria host the Calabar Carnival variously tagged as “Africa’s biggest street party”, “the pride of Nigeria”. This paper presents a Carnival event that was held from the first day of December to the last day of December 2024 in Calabar, The event is an “integrated Carnival package” comprising of main carnival with Caribbean (Trinidadian Carnival) costumes, children carnival, night of kings and queens, cultural carnival and international Ekpe (Leopard) masquerade festival, biking carnival, carnival night of music (secular and gospel and jokes, as well as Christmas carnival carol night. The massive and integrated nature of the annual carnival evidently puts Cross River State as a tourism destination in Nigeria.

Keywords: Caribbean-Calabar Relationship, Carnival costume, street party, children carnival, carnival kings and queens, Ekpe (Leopard) masquerade, Cross River State

INTRODUCTION

Calabar Carnival is a 31-day annual event (December 1st to December 31st) that takes place on the streets of Calabar, the capital city of Cross River State in Nigeria (**Figure 1**). The Carnival has served as a key opportunity for Cross River State to establish itself as a tourism destination in Nigeria and gain recognition on the global tourism map. In 2004, then-Civilian Governor Mr. Donald Duke initiated the event. To institutionalize the Carnival, his government established the Cross River State Carnival Commission.

What began as a blend of African cultural festivals and Caribbean Carnival aesthetics has evolved into a hybrid of various street dance styles, parades, religious and secular music performances, parade of costumes, floats, masquerades, night of jokes, and an infusion of African and Caribbean cultural aesthetics.

Hotels and other accommodations are fully booked by September in preparation for December, as the event attracts international visitors and tourists from other states in Nigeria. The festive atmosphere of Christmas and Carnival begins at the start of December, with public spaces like the city gate and roundabouts adorned with beautiful decorations, as shown in **Photos 1 and 2**. Road roundabout welcomes travelers arriving in Calabar by road from other states with a new look as seen in **Photo 3**. The rich fusion of Africa’s native culture and the highly admired Caribbean carnival costumes is visible in **Photos 4 to 178**. The event is often referred to as Africa's biggest street party. Calabar is also known for its historical significance as a former famous slave port in southeastern Nigeria during the trans-Atlantic slave trade in the Bight of Biafra.

More than twenty years after its inception, the carnival has achieved global acclaimed and universal participation, attracting over a million attendees annually, featuring international representation and a strong visual tradition that resonates with Black Atlantic Carnival. The Executive Governor of Cross River State, His Excellency Prince Bassey Otu, along with his wife, Rev. Eyoanwan Bassey Otu, are pictured in **Photos 4 and 5** as they “flag off” the December 2024 Carnival by cutting the tape. In **Photos 8, 9, and 10**, the Governor and his wife lead the carnival procession.

Figure 1. Cross River State of Nigeria with all the eighteen Local Government Areas including Calabar the city capital.

In **Photos 11 and 12**, they can be seen enjoying the performances together. The Calabar Carnival spans 31 days filled with fun and entertainment, expanding each year in terms of activities, participation, and organization.

New events are introduced annually, drawing more visitors and international tourists. **Photos 13 to 63** showcase some of the key carnival participants and activities that highlight Caribbean (Trinidadian Carnival) influences. At the Carnival's inception, the government selected a team of twenty-five individuals to visit Trinidad to participate in and study the Trinidad Carnival comprehensively. The collaboration between Calabar Carnival (CC) and Trini-Carnival (TT) is historically significant, as the Efik people of Cross River and other tribes in southeastern Nigeria share ancestral ties with their Caribbean counterparts, whose ancestors were sold during the trans-Atlantic slave trade, while Trinidadians explore their African roots. Trinidadians participate annually in both the main carnival and the international Ekpe festival.

The Children's Carnival, highlighted in **Photos 64 to 84**, is a new addition to the original concept. A special day is designated within the 31-day event, referred to as the "Children Carnival," where children showcase their talents and teamwork. This aspect of the carnival aims to help children appreciate African culture and foster an interest in their heritage at an early age.

Some activities of the Cultural Carnival are showcased in **Photos 111 to 136**. In addition to the cultural day, a separate day is always set aside for the international Ekpe (Leopard) Society masquerade festival (**Photos 124 – 135**). Calabar is home to the Efiks, Efut, and Quas, and the three tribes share the Ekpe (Leopard) Society as a common heritage, tradition and governance. The Ekpe Society was once the ruling government in Calabar (Efik, Efut, and Qua tribes) before the introduction and adoption of British rule. The Ekpe Society can still be found and treasured in all lands and communities where the tribes had once settled in the course of their migratory history before finally coming to settle in Calabar, Nigeria.

The Ekpe Society, aside from being the cornerstone of traditional governance, served as the primary lawmakers and the centre for uniting the ancient kingdoms of the Efiks, Efuts, and Quas. The Ekpe Society enacts laws that shape communities, enforce the law, and establish culture, justice, peace, and unity across the region and communities. Beyond the Ekpe festival, cultural troupes and performances from the eighteen local government areas of the state, along with participants from various states in Nigeria and other African countries, are included. The beauty of the cultural carnival lies in the fact that everything is authentically African, from the dances to the costumes and the food served.

The Carnival Night of Kings and Queens can be seen in **Photos 85 to 110**; it is a night of competition featuring a parade of colours, costumes, creativity, and innovation. It is always an evening of fun with foreign troupes in attendance, along with top government officials, international guests, tourists, enthusiasts, and residents. The Carnival platform also provided another opportunity for biking activities, as seen in **Photos 138 – 165**. Biking performances were introduced to the Carnival for the first time in 2015. During the bike parade, riders showcase their skills through manoeuvres, tricks, slides, wheelies, bunny hops, and jumps. Bike racing is another thrilling highlight of the day for revellers who line the carnival biking routes to watch and admire various power bikes. For the 2024 carnival, about 200 power bikes participated, covering 12 km with acrobatic and breathtaking stunts.

The carnival night of music brings together local, regional, and international music stars in live performances and concerts, as depicted in **Photos 116 to 170**. The night features both secular and gospel music, with various artists captivating the audience.

The crowd dances and sings along to every song, and as the night concludes, attendees look forward to next year's musical night. One intriguing aspect of the music concert is that local and upcoming musicians are given the chance to showcase their talents.

The Calabar Carnival carol, traditionally held on Christmas Eve, combines the festivities of carols and Nine Lessons. The Christmas carnival carol night is captured in **Photos 171 to 178** and features reading of nine lessons from the Holy Bible. Each lesson read is interspersed with carol melodies. This outdoor event benefits from Calabar's dry and clear weather of December. The Carol night attracts a large crowd that includes the Governor and other senior government officials.

On a lighter note, the carnival of "photo taking" was evident, with all sorts of local and international media cameramen and crews, professional commercial photographers, and "emergency professional photographers" taking the opportunity to capitalise on the one-month livelihood the 31-day carnival celebration has created. Amateur photographers, students with mobile cameras, and researchers, like the authors, also joined the throngs of street photographers wielding their mobile devices.

CONCLUSION

Calabar Carnival, popularly referred to as "Africa's biggest street party," and sometimes "the pride of Nigeria" continues to expand in activities and participation at both national and international levels. This celebration is multicultural, enriched with a significant mix of Caribbean Carnival influences, as seen in the costumes, bands, vibrant street music, dances, and performances. The high content of the Caribbean Carnival in the Calabar Carnival could be attributed to

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Photo 1. Night appearance of a decorated roundabout in Calabar the city capital of Cross River State, Nigeria in West Africa.

Photo 2. Christmas decoration of a roundabout in Calabar, Nigeria as seen in the night.

Photo 3. The first round-about that welcomes all travelling into Calabar by road.

Photo 4. The Governor of Cross River State, Nigeria, His Excellency Prince Bassey Otu and his wife Rev. Eyoanwan Bassey Otu in carnival costume.

Photo 5. The Governor of Cross River State, Nigeria, Prince Bassey Otu and his wife Rev. Eyoanwan Bassey Otu in action to declare the 2024 Calabar Carnival open for participation.

Photo 6. The Governor, His Excellency Prince Bassey Otu cutting the tape to “flag off” the Calabar Carnival 2024. His wife Rev. Eyoanwan Bassey Otu by his left-hand watch with admiration.

Photo 7. His Excellency the Governor of Cross River State Prince Bassey Otu and his wife Rev. Eyoanwan Bassey Otu share pleasantries after cutting that declared the Calabar Carnival 2024 open and for all to participate.

Photo 8. The Governor of Cross River State Prince Bassey Otu and his wife Rev. Eyoanwan Bassey Otu in Calabar Carnival 2024 road walk.

Photo 9. His Excellency the Governor of Cross River State Prince Bassey Otu and his wife Rev. Eyoanwan Bassey Otu leading the Carnival 2024 procession.

Photo 10. The Cross River State number one citizen His Excellency Prince Bassey Otu and his wife Rev. Eyoanwan Bassey Otu lead the Carnival 2024 street party.

Photo 11. The Cross River State number one citizen Prince Bassey Otu and his wife Rev. Eyoanwan Bassey Otu seated and watching the Carnival float, walk, dance and performance.

Photo 12. Carnival enthusiasts took opportunity to share pleasantries with the Governor and his wife during the carnival.

Photo 13. Parade of flag of sponsors organizations of the Calabar Carnival 2024.

Photo 14. Team of judges positioned along the street (carnival way) to score the different groups and bands as they perform, dance and walk through carnival designated street of Calabar.

Photo 15. Another team of judges' positioned along the street (carnival way) to score the different groups and bands as they perform and walk through the designated street.

Photo 16. The Governor of Cross River State and his wife leading the Calabar carnival 2024 street walk.

Photo 17. A group in carnival costumes display dancing steps.

Photo 18. Ladies in carnival costumes and carnival spirit.

Photo 19. A group in carnival costumes display dancing steps.

Photo 20. A group in carnival costumes display dancing steps.

Photo 21. Carnival enthusiasts with their costumes.

Photo 22. Ladies dancing to loud street music during the carnival parade.

Photo 23. A carnival enthusiast dressed in Caribbean-inspired carnival costume.

Photo 24. A carnival enthusiast on street parade with the crowd catching glimpse of the street dance and beautiful costumes.

Photo 25. A carnival enthusiast dressed in carnival costume.

Photo 26. A carnival enthusiast dressed in carnival costume.

Photo 27. Carnival enthusiasts dressed in carnival costume.

Photo 28. Carnival enthusiasts posed for photography during the street walk and dance.

Photo 29. Carnival street dance and performance.

Photo 30. Ladies in beautiful carnival costumes.

Photo 31. Ladies in beautiful carnival costumes.

Photo 32. Carnival enthusiast.

Photo 33. Street performance during the Calabar carnival 2024.

Photo 34. Street display during the carnival road walk and dance.

Photo 35. Carnival enthusiasts pose in front of a Christmas village Kiosk.

Photo 36. Road performance.

Photo 37. Carnival road performance.

Photo 38. Street performance.

Photo 39. Street dance and performance.

Photo 40. Carnival street walk.

Photo 41. Street performance.

Photo 42. One of the carnival queens in street performance.

Photo 43. One of the carnival kings in street performance.

Photo 44. Lady in carnival performance.

Photo 45. Carnival participants in high mode and spirit.

Photo 46. The physically challenged participated in the Calabar Carnival.

Photo 47. Spectators seated in canopies set along the street to watch the carnival (street party)

Photo 48. Carnival enthusiasts posed for photograph during the street walk.

Photo 49. Carnival enthusiasts pose for photography during the street walk.

Photo 50. The red cross costumes team were handy.

Photo 51. Carnival street dance and performance.

Photo 52. Carnival street dance and performance.

Photo 53. Carnival group street performance.

Photo 54. Ladies showing enthusiasm as they participate in Calabar Carnival 2024.

Photo 55. The Governor and wife admire the carnival groups as they walk, and dance pass his canopy.

Photo 56. Carnival enthusiasts dressed in carnival costume seated and enjoying themselves while watching the carnival performances.

Photo 57. Carnival enthusiasts in her costume.

Photo 58. Carnival enthusiasts seated and watching the carnival street performances.

Photo 59. Carnival enthusiasts seated and watching the carnival performances.

Photo 60. Carnival enthusiasts seated and watching the carnival performances.

Photo 61. Carnival enthusiasts seated and watching the carnival performances.

Photo 62. Carnival enthusiasts seated and watching the carnival performances.

Photo 63. Carnival enthusiasts seated and watching the carnival performances.

Photo 64. Children participated in the carnival with their costumes.

Photo 65. Children participated in the carnival with their costumes.

Photo 66. Children in carnival street dance and performance.

Photo 67. Children street walk and performance.

Photo 68. Children in Carnival Street performance.

Photo 69. Children participated in cultural carnival.

Photo 70. Girl carnival queen.

Photo 71. Children participating in the carnival street performance.

Photo 72. Street walk and display.

Photo 73. Children enjoying themselves during the carnival street walk.

Photo 74. Children participating in the carnival with their costumes.

Photo 75. Children Carnival Street dance and performance.

Photo 76. Boy carnival king.

Photo 77. Children in carnival costumes.

Photo 78. Girl carnival queen.

Photo 79. Girl carnival queen of a group.

Photo 80. Young girls in high carnival spirit.

Photo 81. Children in cultural carnival street dance and performance.

Photo 82. Girls in a cultural carnival street performance.

Photo 83. Carnival street performance.

Photo 84. Street performance during the carnival.

Photo 85. Display of a carnival queen and her costume.

Photo 86. Display of a carnival king and his costume.

Photo 87. Display of a carnival queen and her costume.

Photo 88. Display of a carnival king and his costume.

Photo 89. Display of a carnival queen and her costume.

Photo 90. Display of a carnival king and his costume.

Photo 91. Display of a carnival queen and her costume.

Photo 92. Display of a carnival king and his costume.

Photo 93. Display of a carnival queen and her costume.

Photo 94. Display of a carnival queen and her costume.

Photo 95. Display of a carnival queen and her costume.

Photo 96. Display of a carnival king and his costume.

Photo 97. Display of a carnival king and his costume.

Photo 98. Display of a carnival queen and her costume.

Photo 99. Display of a carnival queen and her costume.

Photo 100. Display of a carnival king and his costume.

Photo 101. Display of a carnival queen and her costume.

Photo 102. Display of a carnival king and his costume.

Photo 103. Display of a carnival queen and her costume.

Photo 104. Display of a carnival king and his costume.

Photo 105. Display of a carnival queen and her costume.

Photo 106. Display of a carnival king and his costume.

Photo 107. Display of a carnival queen and her costume.

Photo 108. Display of a carnival king and his costume.

Photo 109. Display of a carnival king and his costume.

Photo 110. Display of a carnival king and his costume.

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Photo 115. Maiden in moninkim attire during the cultural carnival display.

Photo 116. Cultural display during the carnival.

Photo 117. Cultural display during the carnival.

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Photo 119. Nigerians from Western part of Nigeria participated in 2024 cultural carnival.

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Photo 122. Women group in street parade with spectator standing on both sides of the road catching the fun with some filming and capturing the moment with camera phones.

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Photo 126. Ekpe (Leopard) masquerade display with spectators watching.

Photo. 127. Ekpe masquerades initiates singing, drumming and dancing.

Photo 128. Masquerade display during the cultural carnival.

Photo 129. Ekpe chiefs with walking up and dancing to the traditional drumming and talking drum.

Photo 130. Masquerade in display performance.

Photo 131. Ekpe chiefs during the Ekpe international festival.

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Photo 133. Masquerade display during cultural carnival.

Photo 134. A cross section of participants at the cultural carnival.

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Photo 138. Speech making time before the start of bikers' carnival.

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Photo 142. Bike race at Calabar 2024 carnival.

Photo 143. Bike race at Calabar 2024 carnival.

Photo 144. Bike race at Calabar 2024 carnival.

Photo 145. Bike race at Calabar 2024 carnival.

Photo 146. Biking as fun at Calabar 2024 carnival.

Photo 147. Biking as fun at Calabar 2024 carnival.

Photo 148. Biking as fun at Calabar 2024 carnival.

Photo 149. Biking at Calabar 2024 carnival.

Photo 150. A biker at Calabar 2024 carnival.

Photo 151. Biking as fun at Calabar 2024 carnival.

Photo 152. Biking as fun at Calabar 2024 carnival.

Photo 153. Biking as fun at Calabar 2024 carnival.

Photo 154. Biking race at Calabar 2024 carnival.

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Photo 162. Maiden in traditional attire.

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